

Nano-Cars and Buckyball Pyramids

by Marek T. Michalewicz
CSIRO Supercomputing Support Group,
CSIRO Mathematical and Information Sciences
Carlton, Victoria, Australia

One of the most interesting and challenging goals of nano-technology in the coming years will be the construction of "Buckyball Pyramids." Here, I will present the rationale for their creation, and then discuss the scientific requirements and sociological implications.

Technologically, transportation of a large number of buckyballs poses a serious problem. I propose building the smallest possible car, a nano-car. The size of this engineering artifact would be, as the name suggests, approximately 10^{-9} meters. This is a billion times smaller than currently popular street automobiles. I also propose applying this to very large scale (on the order of 10^6 cars) Intelligent Vehicle Systems and to big cities traffic simulations.

The Need for Buckyball Pyramids

Each civilisation builds a great pyramid to commemorate its greatness. Examples abound in Egypt and in Aztec and Mayan civilisations. In modern times, we have seen the construction of the Pompidou Centre in Paris and the Parliament House in Canberra, Australia. Time and again, civilizations have constructed huge and monumental things. The mere goal of building a gigantic structure no longer poses a satisfyingly original challenge. The twenty-first century should, therefore, be celebrated by the building of *very small pyramids*. It is chemically and aesthetically fitting that the best building block for tiny pyramids would be the C_{60} molecule, commonly known as a "Buckyball."

Buckyball pyramids will find use in a wide range of areas—as Christmas season novelties, as collectors' items (collect them all?), and in the SETI effort to find and communicate with alien civilizations (we will offer Buckyball pyramids as

Figure 2. A ball and stick representation of a "Molecular Ferric Wheel." The black balls are Fe ions.

proof of our civilisation's superior intelligence and ability to control matter). Buckyball pyramids will also be useful in precision investigations of claims of paranormal pyramid "energy."

But now we are confronted with a serious technological issue: How

can we efficiently cart around these tiny, tiny Buckyballs? To solve this problem, I propose here all of the construction elements necessary to build a nano-car.

The idea of a tiny little car first surfaced in a paper written by Richard Feynman.¹ However, Feynman speculated only about a *micro-car*, a car only approximately 4000 times smaller than an automobile. I, in contrast, push the limit as far as "molecularly possible, and propose construction of a nano-car, with linear dimensions of approximately 30 angstroms by 20 angstroms by 20 angstroms. The basic laws of physics show that it should be possible to build such a tiny engineering artifact.

In the following sections I list all the required molecular "subparts" needed to build a nano-car. I look briefly at the construction process, do a quick cost analysis, and then propose other uses for a nano-car. I conclude with some general remarks on the likely sociological impact of this grandly tiny engineering feat.

Molecular Ingredients

The necessary structural elements are: four "Ferric wheels"; two struts of the type known as "staffenes"; a graphitic sheet; and, as reinforcing elements, several buckytubes.

One novel feature of our design is the propulsion system. It is embedded in the (antiferromagnetic) wheels which interact magnetically with the "road," or atomic substrate.

There could be no car, nor even a cart, without a wheel. The wheels of a nano-car will be four $[Fe(OMe)_2(O_2CCH_2Cl)]_{10}$ molecules, affectionately called "molecular ferric wheels."²

The axles will be made of $[n]$ Staffenes. These molecular-size tinkertoys have been synthesized and described in detail by J. Michl, his co-workers and others.³⁻¹⁰

Figure 1. Structure of a C_{60} Buckyball molecule.

Figure 3. A ball representation of two $[n]$ Staffenes: (a) oligomer of $[1.1.1]$ propellane, $n=6$ (left) and (b) $[6]$ cubane (right).

The remaining elements of the nano-car construction set will be a two-dimensional graphitic sheet which will join the two axles together, and some nanotubes to provide greater structural rigidity and strength. The simple

details of how to assemble a nano-car are best left to technologists and engineers to sort out. It is likely they will use of abstraction molecular tools¹¹ of some sort.

The Drive System

One of the most intriguing features of a nano-car is its drive system.

The "engine" is hidden in the wheels. Taft *et al.*² reported the first study of the magnetic properties of antiferromagnetic "ferric wheels." I have no doubt that by manipulating various time- and length-dependent characteristics of an external magnetic field, one can devise a variety of ways to accelerate, decelerate and steer a nano-car. The details of these interactions are crucial, and are best left to technologists and engineers to sort out.

Some Uses for Nano-Cars

There are many obvious uses for a nano-car. Exhaustive exploration of all the possibilities would take us outside the main topic of this paper, which is nothing less than a feasibility study for building Buckyball Pyramids and nano-cars. However some of the other obvious applications of a nano-car include: simulating traffic patterns of whole cities (e.g. Mexico City); accurate drug delivery on a nano-scale; performing courier activities; and, of course, building Buckyball Pyramids.

Conclusions

The concept of miniaturisation has played an important role in the development of modern technological society. We are on the verge of breakthroughs that will bring us to the ultimate physical limits of miniaturisation. Building a nano-car will make it possible to build Buckyball Pyramids, but it is also an enterprise worth pursuing for its own right. Perhaps most important, it constitutes the next big challenge for the automotive industry.

The philosophical and social implications of this invention are hard to predict. We can be sure only that its size and the requisite mass scale of manufacture will

make global civilisation more egalitarian and just. Perhaps we will see a day when there is one Buckyball Pyramid and one nano-car for each and every person on earth.

Humankind constantly desires to "outdo" both earlier generations and contemporaries. The race among nations to dominate the world, which has been so beneficial in bringing about space exploration, the landing of humans on the moon, the collapse of communism, and the end of the Cold War, is still being run. The first nation to win in the nanoscopic world will, on a more prosaic level, achieve the domination of all nations and macroscopic objects.

Acknowledgments

I thank Professor Diana Guenzburger for bringing the "Molecular Ferric Wheel" to my attention. Our ferric wheel molecular diagram was built using the Cerius2 program with input parameters from the book by Taft *et al.*² All other molecules and molecular fragments were built and optimised using the UniChem suite of Quantum Chemistry programs.

References

- 1 "There's Plenty of Room at the Bottom," R. Feynman, *Engineering and Science*, Cal Tech, Feb. 1960; also at: <http://nano.xerox.com/nanotech/feynman.html>
- 2 K.L. Taft, C.D. Delfs, G.C. Papaefthymiou, S. Foner, D. Gatteschi and S.J. Lippard, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, vol. 116, 1994, pp. 823-32.
- 3 "Nanoworlds are made of this," R. Pease, *New Scientist*, June 10, 1995, pp. 26-9.
- 4 R.C. Merkle, *Nanotechnology*, vol. 2, 1991, pp. 134-41.
- 5 J. Michl, P. Kaszynski, A.C. Friedli, G.S. Murthy, H-Ch. Yang, R.E. Robinson, N.D. McMurdie and T. Kim, in: *Strain and Its Implications in Organic Chemistry*, A. de Meijere and S. Blechert (Eds.), Kluwer Academic, 1989, pp. 463-82.
- 6 P. Kaszynski, A.C. Friedli and J. Michl, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, vol. 114, 1992, pp. 601-20.
- 7 P. Kaszynski, *From [1.1.1]propellane to Tinkertoys*, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Texas at Austin, 1991.
- 8 A-D. Schlüter, *Macromolecules*, vol. 21, 1988, pp. 1208-11.
- 9 A-D. Schlüter, H. Bothe and J-M Gosau, *Macromolecular Chemistry*, vol. 192, 1991, pp. 2497-519.
- 10 K. Hassenrück, G.S. Murthy, V.M. Lynch and J. Michl, *Journal of Organic Chemistry*, vol. 55, 1990, pp. 1013-6.
- 11 C.B. Musgrave, J.K. Perry, R.C. Merkle and W.A. Goddard III, *Nanotechnology*, vol. 2, 1991, pp. 187-95.

